

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MEMBERSHIP

The National Network of Libraries of Medicine (NNLM) Regional Medical Libraries (RMLs) prioritize building strong relationships with their members to foster collaboration and achieve shared goals. Each region focuses on specific strategies to engage members and enhance the network of committed organizations.

Themes include:

- Recruiting and engaging active members through training, outreach, and promotion of NNLM membership on websites.
- Improving communication with existing and new members, increase representation from diverse groups, and establish advisory boards.
- Actively engaging with professional organizations, presenting at conferences, and providing guidance on grant applications.
- Interacting with regional MLA (Medical Library Association) chapters, targeting Minority Serving Institutions, and requiring NNLM membership for education and training events.
- Identifying areas lacking membership, targeting new audiences, refining communication strategies, and focusing outreach in underserved areas.

EDUCATION & TRAINING

Regional medical libraries play an important role in providing education and training to member organizations, helping to improve the skills and knowledge of their member organizations, and ultimately enhancing the services they provide to their communities.

RMLs tend to determine special regional needs through:

- Regional Advisory Boards
- NNLM-based Membership Survey
- NNLM-based Training Survey
- Discussions with Leaders in Target Populations

RMLs identified special needs, such as:

- Data Science
- Public Health
- Information Access
- Consumer Health

RMLs met these needs through regional initiatives, such as:

- Webinars and Meetings
- Professional Development Opportunities
- Social Media Engagement

SUBAWARDS

NNLM subawards provide the necessary financial support for individuals and organizations to carry out projects that improve access to health information, increase engagement with research and data, expand professional knowledge, and promote awareness and use of NLM resources in local communities. Below is some basic information about grant funding from Year 1.

- NNLM Regions funded 124 total projects in Grant Year 1
- NNLM Regions gave out \$1.3M to funded projects in Grant Year 1.

NNLM Regions funded:

- 85 projects to advance health equity by reducing health disparities,
- 95 projects to advance health literacy, and
- 114 projects to engage, train, support individuals from underrepresented racial-ethnic minority populations

Major themes in NNLM Subaward proposals, included:

- Management and acquisition of diverse collections of materials
- Role of NLM in providing resources and training, and using digital platforms
- Role of language and digital literacy in addressing health concerns
- Measurement and improvement of outcomes in public health

COLLABORATIONS

Collaborating with other members of the network creates a more effective and efficient network through shared expertise, resource sharing, increasing reach, and building relationships. Collaborations can ultimately lead to a greater impact in achieving the shared goals and objectives of the network.

All ROCs collaborated with each other ROC in all mandatory working groups, ad-hoc committees, and several network-wide and cross-regional projects in Grant Year 1. These initiatives demonstrate the active engagement of each region to improve NNLM's programs, services, and inclusivity. Local collaborations with communities or non-NNLM members as well as other external collaborations, those which go beyond the NNLM ROCs and their staff, were less often reported than internal or traditional collaborations.

NEC'S RECOMMENDATIONS

Future NNLM Impact Reports would benefit from:

- Continue efforts to leverage federal standards and persistent identifiers and apply consistently; incorporate Common Data Elements into workflows; establish standard definitions and labels for RMLs to use to capture meaningful information and describe concepts such as general topics (e.g., "Health Disparities"), subaward themes, special regional needs, and collaborations.
- More detailed data: we want to hear about your stories not just aggregate numbers. How do you understand "impact" at the local/regional/ROC level? Tell us more about the actual mechanisms that you use internally to gauge engagement, to provide guidance and determine needs. Share with us the lessons you have learned when going through your own data. Finally, whenever possible, we would love to see any training, outreach materials/visuals your ROCs create. They would help us illustrate your accomplishments.